

***In silico* study of pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) – isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 as a potent drug against *Candida* species**

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Abstract : Increased incidence of candidiasis has been reported in immunocompromised patients. The aim of the present study was to predict the molecular interaction between pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) (PPDHP) extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 against the selected candidal proteins responsible for virulence. The compound PPDHP was extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 and identified by spectral studies. The interaction of the lead compound with the selected target proteins 2Y7N, 2QZW, 1IYK, 2WUZ and 2X7N was analysed by molecular docking studies. The anticandidal activity (MIC) of the compound against the selected *Candida* species was < 2 µg/mL. Among the target proteins, the compound showed least binding energy of -283.58 kcal/mol against 1IYK, -250.62 kcal/mol against 2WUZ and -188.91 kcal/mol against 2X7Q. Both *in vitro* and *in silico* studies with the compound suggest that the lead could be used as anticandidal compound against candidiasis.

Keywords : *Streptomyces*, *Candida* species, *In silico* molecular docking, pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl), anticandidal activity.

Introduction

Candida albicans grows in the oral cavity and gastrointestinal tract as commensal organism¹. It is opportunistic pathogen and has been reported to be life threatening in immunocompromised patients. The search for new efficient drugs against candidal infection has become more and more important as the frequency of infection has increased in immunocompromised and cancer patients². The dysfunction of immune system can allow switching from a commensal to a pathogenic organism that is capable of causing fatal diseases³⁻⁵. The clinical spectrum of *C. albicans* infections ranges from mucocutaneous to systemic life-threatening infections⁶. In this context, the virulence factor responsible for the pathogenesis needs to be emphasised⁷. *C. albicans* pathogenesis is complex and multifactorial in nature⁸. They possess several virulence factors like host recognition biomolecules (adhesins), phenotyping switching and phospholipases etc.⁹. Being dimorphic, they have the ability to change between yeast and hyphal cells which is the major virulence factor. The pathogenesis involves adhesion and penetration of the hyphal cells from a colonized mucosal site to internal parenchyma organs such as liver and pancreas¹⁰. It was

reported that secreted aspartate proteinases (Sap 1-9) are among those factors of the human pathogen *C. albicans*, which promote infections in the immunocompromised host¹¹. Inhibition of the virulence factors would be the best target for the emerging anticandidal drugs. Docking studies have been used to find out and to identify the possible interaction of the particular compound with the selected target¹². In the present study the compound PPDHP extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 was studied for its interaction with the selected target proteins of *Candida* by *in silico* approach and drug likeliness.

Experimental

Isolation and identification of the compound :

Streptomyces sp. VITPK9 was isolated from sediment collected from salt-spring located in Thoubal district, Manipur, India¹⁵. The bioactivity guided extraction and purification yielded the anticandidal compound pyrrolo-[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) and served as ligand. The canonical smiles of the compound were obtained from Chemspider (online tool for chemical database). Using CORINA 2.54 (online tool for generation of 3D structure) the copied canonical SMILES were

pasted to get the pdb format file with 3D structure of the compound.

Receptors and Ramachandran plot analysis :

C. albicans proteins responsible for virulence were chosen according to the earlier reports¹⁶. The targeted proteins were N-terminal domain of ALS, SAP 1, myristoyl transferase, cytochrome 51 and periplasmic binding protein (PBP) and their PDB ID were 2Y7N, 2QZW, 1IYK, 2WUZ and 2X7Q respectively. The 3D structures of the proteins were downloaded from Protein Data Bank databases. Prediction of the active sites of the target proteins were done using Q-site finder online tool. The target proteins were analysed by Ramachandran plot using PROCHECK to check the quality of the proteins^{17,18}.

Molecular docking :

Patch Dock online tool was used for molecular docking studies (<http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/PatchDock/>). The targeted proteins serves as the receptors and the extracted compound (PPDHP) serves as the ligand. The input files are in PDB file format and RMSD is required for final clustering stage of the algorithm. Both the input files are uploaded followed by the E-mail address and the default value for RMSD parameter is 4 Å. For this study we set the complex as protein-small ligand docking. The docked result was viewed by "Pymol 1.3" software¹².

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) value :

MIC value of the compound was determined by broth dilution method recommended by NCCLS guidelines. Stock solution of the standard antibiotic was prepared as the positive control. The compound PPDHP was prepared dissolving in DMSO to make a concentration range of 100–0.78 µg/mL by broth dilution method¹⁹.

Results and discussion

Extraction of *Streptomyces* sp.VITPK9 yielded anticandidal compound (PPDHP) with the molecular formula C₁₄H₁₆O₂N₂ and serves as the ligand. The PDB file with the 3D structure of the compound was downloaded using Corina. Using Autodock tool the ligand was identified to have 15 non-polar hydrogen, 6 aromatic carbon and 2 rotatable bonds.

Receptors :

The structure of the selected five target proteins of *C. albicans* were downloaded from Protein Data Bank with their respective PDB ID. The active sites of the proteins were identified and found to have 10 active sites each.

Ramachandran plot analysis :

The Ramachandran plot analysis of the target proteins i.e. 2Y7N, 2QZW, 1IYK, 2WUZ and 2X7Q revealed that all the target proteins were of excellent choice as the percentage residues of the most favoured region of the proteins range from 86–89% (above the cut-off 75%) (Table 1).

Molecular docking :

The output file of the docking was received through E-mail, which showed all possible docking score between the receptor and ligands. The ligand was docked with all the selected target proteins. The compound PPDHP showed the least binding energy of –283.58 kcal/mol with 1IYK, with 2WUZ –250.62 kcal/mol and with 2X7Q –188.91 kcal/mol. Along with the score, area, ACE (Atomic contact energy), transformation, and the PDB file of the complex was also given with the report (Table 2). Two sites of interaction were observed with 2Y7N and the amino acid TYR residue was involved in two sites of interac-

Table 1. Ramachandran plot analysis

	2Y7N		2Q2W		1IYK		2WUZ		2X7Q	
	C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2	C1	C2
Most favoured regions	238	87.28	510	86.7	624	89.1	685	89.0	258	92.1
Additional allowed regions	31	11.4	72	12.2	74	10.6	80	10.4	21	7.5
Generously allowed regions	3	1.1	5	0.9	2	0.3	0	0.0	0	0.0
Disallowed regions	1	0.4	1	0.2	0	0.0	5	0.6	1	0.4

Table 2. Molecular docking report of the PPDHP

Compound	Target proteins	PDB ID	Score	Area	ACE
C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	Myristoyl transferase	1IYK	3840	436.80	-283.58
	Cytochrome 51	2WUZ	4284	457.30	-250.62
	Periplasmic binding protein	2X7Q	3830	461.60	-188.91
	N-Tenninal domain of ALS	2Y7N	3886	430.40	-159.88
	SAP 1	2QZW	4288	478.60	-94.12

tion. The length of the interaction was calculated to be 3.6 Å and 2.6 Å respectively with protein 2QZW, no amino acid was found to be involved in the interaction. The length of the interaction of the ligand with protein 1IYK was found to be 2.9 Å. ASN residue at 106th position was involved in interaction with ligand. LEU (208th) and PRO (39th) residues of 2WUZ were found to interacted with the ligand with 2.5 Å and 3.3 Å length of interaction respectively. PRO at the 39th position of the protein 2X7Q interacted with the ligand. The schematic diagram of the docked image of the proteins with the compound is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The interaction of the lead compound PPDHP with the selected candidal proteins.

Minimum Inhibition Concentration (MIC) value :

MIC is the lowest concentration where there is no visible growth. The lead compound showed MIC value of 1.56 ± 0.12 µg/mL against *C. albicans*, 0.78 ± 0.14 µg/mL against *C. krusei* and 1.56 ± 0.04 µg/mL against *C. tropicalis*. Fluconazole was used as the positive control. Several approaches have been developed to counteract the rise of candidal infection. In this study, the use of *in vitro* and *in silico* tools made it possible to understand

the possible pharmaceutical and pharmacokinetics of the lead compound extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9. The compound PPDHP showed much lower MIC value against *Candida* species signifying its anticandidal potential. The recent application of *in silico* pharmacology tools with the *in vitro* studies would pave way in development of potential drug candidate with fewer side effects. The 3D structure of *C. albicans* CA3427 gene product was solved and stated that it would be the potential target for the emerging new antifungal drugs¹³. 1IYK encodes for N-meristoyl transferase, which is an attractive target of new antifungal candidate¹⁴. Since the lead compound PPDHP showed strong interaction with the three most important drug target proteins 1IYK, 2WUZ and 2X7Q, it can serve as potential anticandidal drug. Many *in silico* approaches were made against 2WUZ as the target protein but very few attempts were made with other proteins involved in pathogenesis. Hence targeting these proteins is much use to decide the candidate drug against *Candida* pathogens.

Conclusion

Based on our findings, pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) could be evaluated further by *in vivo* studies to develop as anticandidal drug.

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